

High level group of EU – expert contributions for recommendation

1. What major challenges (scientific, social, economic, technological) should still be attempted to be addressed in the second half of HE (2025-27) and further addressed by a future FP (FP10)?

Food value chains are the most impacting of any industries, agriculture and food activities generating up to a third of global emissions: lowering the sustainable impact of food systems is a necessity and can only be a positive investment for Europe, as confirmed by recent EU reports and the EIT Food Think Tank. Recent years have also shown how climate change can impact and affect supply chains, even generate shortages: some ingredients are already at risk and it's clear that this topic is underestimated. The recently unveiled Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Initiative is a positive sign from EU institutions which have clearly stressed how food and agriculture shall be included as beneficiary industries of the future progress on these technologies

Any of these key topics shall be reflected much more strongly in the coming HE 2025-2027.

Challenges that we have identified are related to the level of knowledge regarding emerging, high tech food production methods such as precision fermentation and cultured meat/seafood, which remain low. Therefore, there is a need to mobilize the community of high-level researchers, from different fields, to direct their work to address technological gaps required for the production of sustainable, nutritious, and ethical food - able to improve the resilience of the food systems in Europe and worldwide.

In particular, we lack publicly available data with which to make accurate assessments of their viability for commercial application as well as cost/benefit analyses regarding other food production methods to mitigate negative impacts (e.g. environment, health, etc) from current intensive animal agriculture. Therefore, one of the major challenges is the creation of fundamental knowledge, novel technologies, and more efficient bioprocesses, that are openly accessible to academics and industry. Such precompetitive knowledge is crucial to foster new and incumbent companies to create novel sustainable food products able to reach the final consumer.

While Horizon Europe has invested in studies to assess the current development and outline future prospects for different types of food production systems, (e.g. FEASTS for cultured meat), the development of a novel resilient food system will require ongoing efforts for many years ahead.

Another crucial challenge relates to training of experts and professionals to support the transition for new food production approaches which requires leveraging on the high quality of education in Europe to build dedicated educational programs.

Importantly, a challenge to which considerable attention has been given in Europe concerns ensuring the safety and nutritional value of novel food, while promoting EU competitiveness in the sector. Indeed, oversight for sustainable foods based on industrial biotechnology approaches (e.g. Novel Foods) should remain with the Commission's Directorate General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE), due to required expertise relevant to ensure consumer safety. Still, the use of existing pathways or drawing novel specific policies for approval of such food is an open issue.

A final challenge to be addressed concerns the development of public-private infrastructure that allows pilot and demonstration scale process development, mitigating initial cost on CAPEX and investors risk, while supporting new companies and promoting food product transition in incumbent companies.

2. Which are the **major successes** of the current HE (2021-2023) and which are the **major "roadblock"/threats for success**?

Current HE 2021-2023 has proved to be strong on agriculture and agroecological transition, as supported by Mission Soil and the numerous Life programs. The ambition to create 100 living labs dedicated to soil health and carbon farming is emblematic of the capability to well address such systemic and holistic issues.

However, and as stated in a recent EIT Food [report](#), less than 1% of the HE budget allocated to food projects over the 10 past years have been deployed on the topic of future proteins: this is paradoxical and harming at a moment when Europe is about to build its future [Protein Strategy](#).

Importantly, the lack of public investment in the sector has led to a failure to develop accurate and usable data for high tech food production sectors (e.g. precision fermentation and cultured meat/seafood) which leaves the public and policymakers reliant on biased information from private developers/entities, and could produce negative outcomes in developing formative policy and regulations. A minor, but still relevant limitation is the current timeframe of the Horizon projects in this sector, which range from 1 to 4 (EU Biofutures and FEASTS is 1 year and 3 years, respectively). This makes it difficult to develop programs able to provide in-depth studies, translate findings into medium/long term actions, as well as monitor and act on results to maximize impact.

3. Which **sub programmes** of HE should be to be **preserved and strengthened in a future FP** (i.e., FP10) and which **should be altered**? How far a future FP (i.e., FP10) should keep/alter the current basic **three-pillar architecture of HE** (i.e., Pillar 1: Excellent Science; Pillar 2: Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness; Pillar 3: Innovative Europe)?

Given the order of magnitude of the stakes to address, the weight of food systems in the economy and their impact on the future of Europe and its resilience, we can only recommend to consider securing a much larger share of the funding on food and agriculture related topics in the future.

Moreover, as food systems are complex and interrelated value chains, some future priority challenges will call for supporting dedicated public private partnerships and Joint Undertakings.

In our view, additional actions to maximize impact may require developing a specialized program and eventually a governing body to support such a program, dedicated to resilient food production. Such action would allow the combination of actions in different pillars, and interaction with EU policy makers to promote co-funding from EU budgets on research and innovation, economic development, agriculture and food safety.

To accelerate the development of a resilient food system, including biotechnology-based foods, it will be interesting to promote not only the strengthening of the scientific system and novel start-up companies, but also to promote the investment/participation of large incumbent companies in consortia fostering and educating conventional food systems to embrace novel food systems.

Such programs should address the previously identified challenges, which include the development of robust science, preferentially openly accessible, to nurture pre-competitive knowledge; pilot and demonstration facilities as hubs to accelerate increase on TRLs with risk mitigation for start-ups and investors; education of experts on the field following multidisciplinary approaches; and provide clear routes for safety and nutritional assessments that contribute to European competitiveness in the field.

4. What would be a **catalyst to overcome current roadblocks of HE** and be implemented in a future FP (i.e., FP10)? What should be **the most important innovations to be considered in a future FP** (i.e., FP10)?

Europe recently named its top 4 critical technologies, including Artificial Intelligence and Biotechnology. Looking at current HE and even the draft 2025 topics, it is clear that these key topics are clearly underestimated if not missing. This is why we advocate to strongly integrate them in the future HE. Among the innovation areas to be covered we highlight: bioinformatics, food omics, AI, bioprocess engineering, genomics and also food environments, sustainability, taxonomy, LCA analysis, supply / biomass foresight analysis,

Note that the EIT Food funded EU Food Biofutures Project, a large consortium including top level European institutions in food biotechnology, will - among other deliverables - be compiling by the end of 2024 a list of the priority R&I topics to be funded by Europe.

Additionally, in the field of cultured food, FEASTS (Dec 2023 - Nov 2026) aims to deliver a roadmap of Cultivate Meat and Seafood; to propose a cross-program database/data sharing platform; to assess and outline further crucial technological tools (cell lines, cell culture media, bioreactors, biomanufacturing, bioprocessing); study the impact of cultured meat on different stakeholders as well as produce a life cycle assessment; and address knowledge gaps on safety and nutrition studies, among other actions. Still, to implement actions resulting from assessments and outlines made in projects such as FEASTS, will require specific programs directed to build a resilient food system.

As mentioned, the relatively short timespan of strategic EU projects will require subsequent maintenance and further expansion of the developed cross-program database/data sharing platforms; allowing for greater synergy between the different stakeholders as well as reducing the need for duplicating data resources, particularly with regard to scientific and technological data; as well as building more knowledge and funding actions to implement the provided recommendations.

August 7th, 2024

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Note: Views and opinions expressed here are only from the authors listed and do not necessarily reflect those of the institutions or consortiums that they take part or lead. Neither from the European Union, REA, EIT nor other funding institutions.

Links:

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_STU\(2024\)757806](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_STU(2024)757806)

<https://www.eitfood.eu/reports/protein-diversification-think-tank-policy-brief>

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_24_1570 <https://feasts-innovation.eu/>

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